

Liquid processable, thermally stable, hydrophobic, phenolic-triazine resins for advanced composite applications

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A commercial phenolic-triazine (PT) oligomer (Primaset™ PT-30) is combined with a second liquid difunctional cyanate ester monomer (Primaset™ LECy) to produce a series of low viscosity, processable reactive blends that are stable at room temperature, display increased thermal stability, while maintaining or improving upon the ultimate properties of the cured materials. The binary blends containing 20 to 25 wt% LECy exhibit low viscosities (<1000 mPa.s) at 50 °C and are considerably more suitable for liquid composite moulding processes when compared with the state-of-the-art commercial matrix, while showing improved moisture performance (reduced by 0.3 wt% after 3127 hours of conditioning at 80 °C and 85% RH), with only minimal loss in thermal performance.

Reactivity & Rheology

- Incorporation of LECy decreases reactivity, but T_g , T_{exo} , and ΔH_c remain relatively constant irrespective of stoichiometry
- Incorporation of 5 wt% of **2** results in a 2-fold drop in viscosity (149 Pa.s)
- As **2** content increases, viscosity of the blend decreases

Figure 1: DSC thermograms of the uncured binary $1_x:2_y$ blends compared to PT-30 (**1**) and LECy (**2**).

Figure 2: Semi-log of complex viscosity against temperature plot of binary $1_x:2_y$ blends.

Longevity & Moisture uptake

Figure 3: Moisture absorption profiles of **1** and binary blend $1_{80}:2_{20}$ when exposed to 80 °C and 85 % relative humidity.

Figure 4: Thermo-oxidative stability of **1** and binary blends $1_x:2_y$ when exposed in air at 250 °C continuously.

- Slight reduction of Y_c (800 °C) with addition of **2**
- PT-30 homopolymer lost 45 % of its mass, compared to 48 % for the binary blend $1_{95}:2_5$ after exposure of 127 days at 250 °C continuous
- After 130 days conditioning in 80 °C and 85 % RH, a mass increase of 5.2 wt% for **1** and 4.9 wt % for $1_{80}:2_{20}$ was observed

Conclusions

1. **Decreased reactivity** - $T_g > 188$ °C of **1**
2. **Better processability** - 2-fold reduction in viscosity via incorporation of 5 wt% of **2**
3. **Better hydrolytic stability** - 0.36 % less moisture ingress after 130 days with incorporation of 20 wt% of **2**
4. **Similar thermal degradation** - Y_c at 800 °C was 62.2 ± 2.3 °C (67.8 °C for **1**)
5. **Similar longevity** - Mass loss after a 64-day period: **1**: 19.21 %, $1_{85}:2_{15}$: 26.49 %, and $1_{75}:2_{25}$: 30.92 %

